

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report describes the published data sets from the nextGEMS production runs.

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WP3

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1 Executive summary

We provide access to a machine readable catalog providing resource locations for the full output of the production simulations for ICON and IFS-FESOM, available to the nextGEMS consortium and the wider scientific community. Data is provided on HEALPix grids on different zoom levels – with a maximal horizontal resolution of about 6.4 km – to optimally support the different scientific objectives. A common dataset is published at [WDCC](#) (World Data Center for Climate)¹ via [doi:10.35095/WDC/nextGEMS_prod_addinfo1](https://doi.org/10.35095/WDC/nextGEMS_prod_addinfo1) (Wieners et al., 2024) and accessible via WDCC.

2 Conclusion & Results

A common dataset resulting from the nextGEMS production simulation phase of the ICON and IFS-FESOM model systems is published as machine readable description with an DOI attributed to it.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling ‘Earth-system’ processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no

¹<https://www.wdc-climate.de>

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
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(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes
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This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP3	Relevance in this deliverable?
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To complete Cycle 3 (Development) simulations (O1).	no
To finalize the configuration (including associated output and data management requirements) of SR-ESMs for the production simulations (O1).	yes
To perform present day and future projections (i.e., production simulations). (O1/O2)	yes
To organize and curate simulation output for sustainable access beyond the completion of NextGEMS. (O1/O2/O3)	yes
To support the four themes in exploring extensions of SR-ESMs to address additional application needs and testing proposed model improvements. (O1/O2/O3)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Building on the [DYAMOND](#)² initiative, within the nextGEMS project the two weather and climate models [ICON](#)³, and [IFS](#)⁴ coupled to the ocean model [FESOM](#)⁵ were developed to simulate 30 years into the future on a storm-resolving scale. The model development was split into three iterative cycles as displayed in Fig 1. In each cycle new features and improvements were implemented and thereupon tested in a simulation spanning at least one annual cycle at 5 km spatial resolution or higher.

Figure 1: The model development is organized in iterative cycles as shown by this graph. The diamonds denote hackathons that evaluate the main simulations towards the end of a project cycle.

4.1 Production simulations

The 30 year production simulations are coupled scenario-based experiments as defined for SSP3-7.0 within the CMIP6 effort (O'Neill et al., 2016), modeling the period 2020-01-01 to 2050-01-01, with both model systems. While ICON was run with a horizontal resolution of 10 km for atmospheric and 5 km for oceanic components, IFS atmosphere used 9 km and FESOM ocean 5 km resolution.

Issues that appeared during and after the cycle 3 hackathon were addressed and are summarized in the next sections.

4.1.1 ICON changes

Atmosphere

Snow – Radiation coupling

Make snow visible in radiation and implement snow optical properties based on effective radius computation (Fu, 1996; Fu et al., 1998; Fu, 2007).

tmx – ICON framework for Turbulent Mixing

Realistic representation at km-scale of the turbulent exchange of water, energy, momentum and matter between the land surface and the atmosphere, and the vertical transport through the boundary layer and up, extending on Hohenegger et al., 2023.

²<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/index.html>

³<https://www.icon-model.org/>

⁴<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/FUG/2+The+ECMWF+Integrated+Forecasting+System++IFS>

⁵<https://fesom.de/>

Improved energy closure

Energy is traced through the system and fixed by adding an adiabatic source term to the thermodynamic equation.

Stratocumulus optical properties

Homogeneity of liquid water clouds is now dependent on lower tropospheric stability, making warmer clouds are more reflective.

Ocean

Vertical resolution

For the multidecadal runs, vertical resolution was reduced from 128 to 72 layers, maintaining high accuracy in the near-surface layers and thus in the ocean-atmosphere interaction while reducing resolution in the deeper ocean layers.

Sea ice

Sea ice modelling was updated due to deficiencies discovered with regards to cycle 3:

- Coupling of wind stress now includes effects of sea-ice cover,
- Adding replacement pressure to sea-ice rheology (Kimmritz et al., 2017),
- Parameter settings (albedo and ocean-ice drag) were harmonized with FESOM.

4.1.2 IFS-FESOM changes

Model code

For IFS and FESOM, no scientific changes were applied with regards to cycle 3.

While reducing IFS horizontal resolution from 4.4 km to 9 km, the deep convection scheme was run with the same reduction of cloud base mass flux that was introduced in cycle 3 for 4.4 km runs.

Output

The output infrastructure was extended to use HEALPix as horizontal discretization for model output.

4.2 Published production model output

Data Catalog

Access to the data is controlled by way of an Intake catalog. This allows for content based instead of location based data usage, making data usage techniques more independent of the actual model output format. The catalog is also the base for the publication to be provided with this deliverable.

Data Structure

Production model output is provided on a number of temporal and spatial resolutions suited to the different scientific topics addressed within nextGEMS.

For the production runs, both models used HEALPix grids for the horizontal discretization (Górski et al., 2005). ICON provides spatial resolutions (zoom levels) from 10 (9 for atmosphere) to 0, IFS-FESOM levels 9 and 7. Level 10 – also referred to as `order 10` or `nside 1024` in HEALPix literature – equates about 6.4 km resolution.

Usage information

Evolving best practices, description and examples are continuously maintained on a dedicated web site, easy.gems⁶

An overview of available datasets is also provided on easy.gems under [nextGEMS pre-final](#)⁷.

4.3 Data access via WDCC

The *production* datasets published in the context of this deliverable are findable and accessible via the WDCC search interface as follows:

Project

[nextGEMS \(Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems\)](#)⁸

Experiment

[nextGEMS: output of the production simulations for ICON and IFS](#)⁹

Dataset description

[nextGEMS: Catalogs of full output of the production simulations for ICON and IFS](#)¹⁰

The published data are globally findable via DOI as

[doi:10.35095/WDCC/nextGEMS_prod_addinfov1](https://doi.org/10.35095/WDCC/nextGEMS_prod_addinfov1)

(Wieners et al., 2024) assigned at the level of the *dataset description*:

In compliance with the [FAIR](#)¹¹ principles, all metadata is openly accessible, while the data download is free for registered users. Interested users can register with WDCC. Further, interoperability is achieved through the ensured use of domain-specific (meta)data and file format standards. Reusability is achieved by supplying a standard license (CC-BY 4.0) and rich, domain-specific metadata.

Details for the actual data access are described on the [easy.gems](#) web site. Currently, a [DKRZ user account](#)¹² is required.

⁶<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/>

⁷<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/prefinal.html>

⁸<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/project?acronym=nextGEMS>

⁹https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_prod

¹⁰https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/entry?acronym=nextGEMS_prod_addinfov1

¹¹<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/info?site=fairness>

¹²https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/getting_started/getting-a-user-account/dkrz-user-account.html#dkrz-user-account

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The nextGEMS *production* data published and made available to the global scientific community in the framework of this deliverable are of very high general interest, since they are among the first publicly available multidecadal dataset with state-of-the-art storm-resolving Earth-system models.

Publication of these data in WDCC facilitates uptake by all stakeholders because

1. WDCC supplied metadata is indexed in various searchable resources, e.g. Google Dataset Search,
2. nextGEMS project reports will reference the data via their unique identifier and provide a citation,
3. project-related communication and dissemination activities, e.g. on the project homepage, will include the data citation in the list of project outcomes,
4. data reuse is very efficient due to the ensured use of domain-specific (meta)data standards which enable allow low-barrier access and analysis of nextGEMS data.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

The model runs were originally planned to be done on the CSC Lumi HPC facility in Finland. However, persistent technical problems (notable hardware errors, immature compiler versions and system software stack for GPUs) delayed the simulations and thus the publication of the output data.

The delay of the work for this deliverable was communicated with and approved by the EC project officer.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Due to the demanding compute and storage resources needed to a km-scale Storm Resolving Model over 30 simulated years in two model instances, the model runs were planned to use the CSC Lumi HPC facility in Finland. Unfortunately, persistent technical problems (notably hardware errors, immature compiler versions and system software stack for GPUs) impeded the schedule prohibitively. Thus we decided to run the production on the DKRZ Levante system at reduced spatial resolution, ie. 10 km for the atmosphere components, while maintaining the 5 km resolution from cycle 3 for the ocean.

9 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This documentation of the production data publication builds a link between the model development teams and the WPs that analyze the model output. In addition, the published data set allows users outside of the immediate nextGEMS community to easily access the simulation output data and thus expanding the reach of nextGEMS results.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2024
- 4th km Scale Hackathon 04. April – 08. April 2024 in Hamburg,
<https://mpim-po.pages.gwdg.de/km-scale-hackathon/>

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website:

<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>